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Subverting Ableist Binaries: An Analysis of the Confluence of Disability Studies and Blue Humanities in Toni Crowther's *From Wheelchair to Water*

Sneha Jacob¹

Abstract

Bodies are in a perpetual state of metamorphosis. The sudden onset of a disability, referred to as an acquired disability, alters all facets of a person's life. In this regard, concepts such as fluidity and instability that remain central to the discipline of blue humanities call for its intersection with disability studies, questioning, for instance, the permanence of the able-bodied/disabled dyad. With reference to the memoir *From Wheelchair to Water* by Toni Crowther (2019), this study attempts to examine the ways in which intersecting both disciplines helps subvert ableist binaries, thereby furthering inclusivity. Through her narrative, Crowther recounts how her passion for swimming gets affected by a life-threatening stroke, leaving her paralysed. The article focuses on how the aquatic environment surrounding Crowther becomes a liberating locale which empowers the disabled body to gain agency and overcome all forms of impediments.

Keywords: Disability Studies, Blue Humanities, Ableist Binaries, Fluidity, Agency

Introduction

In recent times, ecological discourses have shifted their focus from the land to the ocean. Considering the fact that more than seventy per cent of the earth's surface is engulfed by water, coupled with the grave climatic changes that have been unfolding across

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the globe, this shift becomes paramount. The advancement of the notion of ‘blue humanities’ by literary historian Steve Mentz in 2009 initiated the ‘oceanic turn’ in literature, focusing on notions including fluidity, oceanography and ecology. Scholars working in the domain of blue humanities regard the ocean as a societal entity, facilitating studies based on individuals whose lives are associated with and impacted by the ocean.

While theoretical deliberations linking disability with the environment have been emerging lately, the specific association between disability studies and blue humanities remains under-explored. The discipline of disability studies strives to perceive and challenge preconceived notions surrounding the concept of disability, including the able-bodied/disabled dyad. For instance, the dynamic nature of bodies and identities, specifically with regard to acquired disabilities, disrupts the predetermined stability of ableist binaries. As disability theorist Rosemarie Garland-Thomson asserts, disability has become a “way of describing the inherent instability of the embodied self” (5). On this note, certain concepts central to blue humanities, including fluidity and instability, challenge superficial binary oppositions and hierarchies, clearly signalling the importance of examining the two disciplines through an intersectional lens.

With reference to the memoir *From Wheelchair to Water* by Toni Crowther (2019), this article strives to illuminate the ways in which intersecting the academic fields of disability studies and blue humanities provides a space through which ableist constructs can be subverted, thereby furthering inclusivity. Born in New Zealand, Crowther’s entire life pivoted around boats and water, fuelling her ardent passion for swimming. The narrative describes her traumatic transition from a healthy mother of an eight-month-old baby to enduring the harrowing repercussions of a life-altering stroke at the age of thirty-five that renders her incapacitated. Nevertheless, the emancipatory power of the aquatic ecosystem surrounding her helps Crowther realise that paralysis can never keep her at bay. The study aims to analyse how the agential potential of the aquatic environment liberates the disabled body from all forms of limitations.

Analysis

Crowther begins her narration by recalling the day she was travelling with her family to a nearby island on their new boat to celebrate Christmas, the evening of which transformed her life in perpetuity. She remembers waking up that night and sensing a strange feeling. Her husband helped her stand up, only for her to collapse on the floor. Crowther was rushed to the hospital, where she found out that she had suffered a stroke and that recovery would take a long time. She was confused and shocked, wondering how a “young, fit and perfectly healthy” body could suddenly be paralysed (Crowther 15).

This traumatic incident that Crowther encountered serves as a reminder that bodies are in a constant state of flux. After years of living as an ‘able-bodied’ individual, the sudden onset of a disability drastically altered every aspect of Crowther’s life, engulfing her with feelings of fear and distress. A relentless desire for a nostalgic past is seen in the lives of individuals with acquired disabilities, “for the lost able mind/body, the nostalgic past mind/body” (Kafer 42). This is evident in Crowther’s narration as her disability was not congenital but acquired during her lifetime, thus instilling within her the yearning to return to the past. She declares, “the whole thing just seemed like a bad dream and I was going to wake up shortly” (14).

The weeks that followed in the hospital were excruciating for Crowther as she found it impossible to perform even simple tasks like going to the bathroom. On a particular day, she felt exhausted waiting for the nurse and tried to get to the commode by herself, only to collapse on the floor. As she remarks, “[it] was so frustrating having to rely on someone to always be there” (16). The special note placed above her, which read ‘assistance required,’ escalated her fury. As the disability theorist Alison Kafer asserts:

people with “acquired” impairments . . . are described (and often describe themselves) as if they were multiple, as if there were two of them existing in different but parallel planes, the “before disability” self and the “after disability” self. . . . the relation between these two selves is always one of loss, and of loss that

moves in only one direction. The “after” self longs for the time “before,” but not the other way around. (42-43)

The above-mentioned incident in Crowther’s life stands as explicit evidence of this statement. Observing her once-healthy body in a paralysed state has been nothing but traumatising for her, and she continually wished to return to her former self.

The medical reports, which revealed the damage that had occurred to her brain, left the doctors perplexed about how Crowther had survived the stroke. Although the doctors were not optimistic about her recovery, Crowther was determined to begin the process and became ecstatic when a bed became available at the rehabilitation unit. However, upon realising that she was the youngest patient there, she recalls her emotional anguish of feeling isolated amidst all the “old, snoring, groaning, disabled patients” (25). As Erin Moser propounds, “for many, acquiring a disability is accompanied by a grieving period [which elicits] intense emotions such as fear, rage, anxiety, discomfort . . . and feelings of alienation” (1). Although Crowther exhibited these feelings, her steadfast resolve to return home propelled her to relearn daily routines, including showering, dressing and walking without assistance.

After ten weeks of physiotherapy, Crowther was allowed to return home. While at home, she constantly felt agitated at her slow progress, as every little task had to be carried out with extreme caution. In her essay on blue cultural disability studies, Katarzyna Ojrzyńska discusses “the trauma of gaining disability and losing the old ways of functioning in the world” (275). This view is exemplified in Crowther’s remark, “it was nice being home, but so tiring that I wasn’t sure how I was going to cope” (43). The comments she received from strangers who shared accounts of their relatives recovering quickly from stroke further exacerbated her anguish. As Ojrzyńska notes, this incident shows “how difficult it is to empathetically respond to the sense of loss that often accompanies acquiring an impairment without taking recourse to stereotypical, often ableist interpretations and narratives of disability” (277). Although Crowther wondered

if she would regain her former self, her determination helped her persevere through the difficult times.

Meanwhile, Crowther came to know about a swimming centre that offered rehabilitation programs in the water. Even though swimming had been her long-standing passion, the extent of her paralysis made her question the viability of the opportunity. Nonetheless, the tenacity that propelled her to make an effort proved beneficial as it elicited significant changes in her. As rightly stated by Ojrzyńska, “the fixedness of the material and social environment [had trapped] the speaker in a narrowly defined role of a helpless victim of fate. By contrast, the . . . openness to potentiality that the watery experience [triggered allowed her] to embrace [her] impaired body” (280). Following months of practice, Crowther gained further mobility and succeeded in swimming her first twenty-five-metre lap, boosting her confidence to a great extent. Moreover, her husband made her a ladder to descend into the water from their boat, providing Crowther with ease and independence. For her, the ladder metaphorically represented a stairway to heaven, connecting her to an environment that she found to be both emancipatory and cathartic, releasing her from the burden of existing preconceptions surrounding her disability.

In the subsequent years, Crowther continued the aquatic therapy and witnessed remarkable improvements in her overall health. Her profound wish to swim for a worthy cause saw her training for a long-distance event in the ocean to raise money for The Stroke Foundation. Despite all her anxieties, through months of arduous training, she completed a long-distance swim of 4.6 kilometres, receiving a rousing reception from a packed audience, including her family. Through several individuals who supported her cause, Crowther raised NZ \$22,000 towards helping stroke survivors, thus making her vision a reality. In her essay, Ojrzyńska asserts that in water, “the sense of weightlessness . . . accentuates the socially-constructed and context-dependent character of disability which . . . dissolves, in an alternative, liquid environment in which solid and fixed ideas . . . no longer hold water” (279-80). It is clear from Crowther's narrative that the aquatic environment questions the

fixedness of ableist binaries, including the able-bodied/disabled dyad, suggesting their impermanence. More importantly, water becomes an agential and liberating environment, enabling Crowther to resist and overcome the limitations imposed upon her by the able-centric world.

Conclusion

Crowther's life serves as a testament to the fact that ableist binaries, such as the able-bodied/disabled dyad, are neither permanent nor impermeable. This idea is encapsulated by the oft-repeated statement that becoming disabled is just a matter of time, be it due to illness, age, or accident. The disability theorists Sharon Snyder, Brenda Brueggemann, and Rosemarie Garland-Thomson refer to this as "the fundamental aspect of human embodiment" (qtd. in Kafer 26). The aquatic environment encircling Crowther plays a vital role in shifting fixed categories and perspectives to that which values fluidity and permeability, as well as acting as an agential body through which Crowther gains resilience. To conclude, Crowther's narrative presents reflections on multiple perspectives of disability in conjunction with the aquatic environment, thereby highlighting the significance of forming alliances between disability studies and blue humanities to subvert ableist discourses and foster inclusivity.

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